

THEORETICAL BASIS OF STUDYING ECONOMIC COMPETENCES OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the theoretical foundations of studying the economic competence of future educators.*

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Today, against the background of economic and cultural reforms in our country, it is of particular importance to know the psychological conditions that ensure the effectiveness of interpersonal relations. In this case, mutual relations cover all areas of human life and serve as one of the necessary conditions for changing the individual and society as a whole. Several of our foreign and local scientists have conducted scientific research within the framework of this problem. For example, G.M.Andreeva, A.A.Bodalev, A.A.Brudniy, L.P.Bueva, Yu.N.Yemelyanov, A.G.Kovalev, A.A.Leontev, B.F.Lomov, G.Marcel, L.B.Filonov, R.Shovin, L.L.Yakubinsky, M.G.Davletshin, E.G.Ozиеv, V.M.Karimova, G.B.Shoumarov, Sh.R.Barotov, N.S.Safaev, U.D.Kadirov, O.E.Hayitov and others can be specially recognized.

Three types of tasks and a complex process structure that arise in interpersonal relations were described by G.M.Andreeva offers this structure in her book "Social Psychology":

- the communicative side of communication, i.e. as a process of interaction or exchange of information between participants in communication;

- the interactive side of communication, i.e. as a process of influencing the behavior of those who enter into communication;

- the perceptive side of communication, that is, as a process related to the perception and understanding of the participants of communication [1].

Uzbek scientist V.M.Karimova [2], focusing on the psychology of communication and interpersonal relations, based on G.M.Andreeva's communication aspects, he expresses his views.

According to V.M.Karimova, if we take it at the scale of society, it can be seen that the behavior of people in different conditions, the management of their behavior depends on certain psychological laws. The reason for this is the various norms and rules adopted in the society [2].

Figure 1.1. The structural aspect of communication according to V.M.Karimova [2]

Because, in the processes of mutual communication and interaction, the images of such behavior are embedded in people's minds, and everyone accepts them as a norm.

It was found that the types and forms of communication are different. For example, this activity is carried out directly "face-to-face" or through one or another technical means (telephone, telegraph, Internet, etc.); being practical or friendly in the course of a professional activity; It can be subject-subject type (diad, triad, tetra, partnership) or subject-object (monological).

Human relations are the processes of interaction in which personal relations are formed and manifested. Such a process initially involves the exchange of thoughts, feelings, worries and joys between people. As people communicate, as their experience of relationships increases, qualities such as commonality, similarity and harmony appear between them, so that they understand each other at a glance or "sentence is clear" and in some cases, the intensity of such communication causes the opposite reactions: getting tired of each other, having nothing left to say. For example, the market environment and relations in it are part of such a close relationship. Only such density can exist not between all members of the market, but between some of its members (seller-buyer, producer-consumer, etc.).

The main goals of the parties entering into a relationship are to get along and understand each other. The complexity, if necessary, the "charm" and uniqueness of this process is that it is impossible for the parties to agree or think and speak exactly the same way. If we were to imagine such a situation, such communication would be the most ineffective and the most ineffective. For example, imagine you went shopping at a store near your home. You asked the seller for the price of the necessary goods, but he gave you the initiative and, no matter what you say, approves you because of the price increase and takes it back. This kind of interaction was very awkward and you would have walked out of the store after dealing with that salesperson as formally as possible the second time around. That is, communication activity is such a condition that the individuality, uniqueness, diversity of knowledge and imagination of each person is manifested in it, and thus it attracts humanity for centuries.

American writer, journalist, political commentator, sociologist W.Lippmann (see Walter Lippmann; 1889–1974), referring to the uniqueness of each human soul and its manifestation in communication, wrote: "Everyone thought the same on earth, no one thinks much", that is, the

primary motive behind people's desire to communicate is to have different views and improve their thoughts during conversations[82].

The analysis of the literature shows that it is possible to get bored and tired of any activity, only a person does not get tired of communication, especially its informal, sincere, direct form, good interlocutors are always spiritually motivated.

A.Abdullaev, K.H.Muftaydinov, H.Aybeshov in the textbook "Managing a small business" (2003) focus on the principles of small business management and describe that entrepreneurship is a socio-economic phenomenon that includes social relations. Acknowledging the existence of legal, psychological, organizational, economic and historical aspects of entrepreneurial activity, scientists emphasize that it is a productive activity in terms of its content and essence.

We study the definitions of a number of scientists during our research and as a result of the analysis of the qualities presented in them, we found out that entrepreneurial activity depends on the internal and external motives of a person. At the basis of any business activity is orientation to spiritual and material needs. The need is manifested in connection with the necessary factors and conditions for the development of a person. Among the factors, one can include the desire to have the resources to financially support the family and loved ones, and of course to manifest oneself as a full-fledged person. We considered the purposeful organization of a system of actions aimed at ensuring that oneself and loved ones live a comfortable and safe lifestyle in the conditions of man-made civilization as a social factor encouraging entrepreneurship.

Also, although the results of entrepreneurial activity arose and developed with the formation of private property and ownership relations, its literal essence is most clearly expressed in the decision of modern business in the conduct of entrepreneurship based on economic freedom [3]. In today's market, none of the producers, consumers and suppliers of goods operate in isolation. Therefore, during the implementation of entrepreneurial activities, the entrepreneur has business relations with his partners [3]. In this case, the relationship between partners is organized on the basis of free information exchange and requires cooperation in solving common problems, developing new types of goods, launching a new project [3].

In our opinion, the individuality, uniqueness, diversity of knowledge and imagination of a person is a mental process of particular importance for future teachers. At the same time, the level of self-awareness and motivation play an important role in the development of economic competence. Through self-awareness, they have a real chance to understand their weaknesses in economic matters and set clear goals for their development.

According to the conclusion given by M.R.Boltaboev and others in the textbook "Small business and entrepreneurship" (2012), entrepreneurship is a special type of economic activity, based on independent initiative, responsibility, entrepreneurial idea, profit. goal-oriented activity lies.

Entrepreneurship is a special type of economic activity, the initial stage of which is usually associated with thinking activity or its result, only then it takes a material form [69].

According to D.Sobirjonova and others, "Management of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship" (2012), there are favorable conditions for the development of entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan. To them:

- high tendency of Uzbeks to introduce new entrepreneurial activities;
- the formation of entrepreneurial activities is compatible with the republican education system;

- high share of the Uzbek people's income allocated to the fund;
- The existence of strong relations between Uzbekistan and the countries of the world;
- Relatively low payment of wages and purchasing power of the population;
- existence of a favorable political environment.

Based on the characteristics of the development of entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, economists distinguish its development into three stages:

Stage 1. We can take the period up to 1917. This period is characterized by the rapid development of small crafts and trade. This period is distinguished by the high level of manual labor, and individual entrepreneurship occupies a special place.

Stage 2. The period from 1917 to 1990. At this time, centrally planned management prevailed. The state played the main role in product production and distribution. Free enterprise activities are relatively limited. Production has been extensively developed. Although the role of small and medium-sized businesses was significant in the first decades of this stage, large enterprises dominated by the last years. For example, if we take the period before the war, about 70% of the total social product of Uzbekistan is small

and medium-sized business enterprises.

Stage 3. We can take the years of the republic after independence. The characteristic aspect of this period is characterized by the prevailing state of "tightness" in the economy, the main task of economic liberalization and stabilization, the need to create a special mechanism for its implementation by the state, and opening a wide path to free entrepreneurship as one of its important ways.

According to K.Moser, enterprises with at least two of the following signs are considered small enterprises, citing the opinion of the American economist Staley. Including:

- 1) personal management of the enterprise by its owner and relatively low specialization;
- 2) the establishment of direct personal relations between the higher management bodies and employees, customers and suppliers of goods;
- 3) complexity of accessing capital markets and obtaining short-term loans;
- 4) lack of a strong position to conclude a transaction;
- 5) strong dependence of the enterprise on relatively nearby markets and supply sources [4].

A.A.Krylov scientifically analyzed entrepreneurial activity in the textbook "Psychology" (1998), saying: "One of the characteristic aspects of market relations is entrepreneurship. "Entrepreneurship is an activity of a citizen directed to taking risks under his own responsibility within the framework of the law, to get profit," he describes. In his opinion, the following factors are the main conditions for the development of entrepreneurship:

- the attitude of state policy to private business;
- public culture and its attitude to the state;
- providing psychological support in business organization;
- a person's talent and abilities for entrepreneurship.

H.D.Hopfner and a group of other experts in the manual "Basics of Business and Entrepreneurship" (2009), based on their research, the following:

- high level of hard work;
- self-confidence;
- know your job well;
- the ability to listen to the opinions of others and the desire to learn;

- initiative;
- ability to withstand failure and overcome;
- ability to act in abstract situations;
- to have honesty and trust;
- ability to take risks;
- build your own future with your own hands;
- striving to achieve one's goals;
- desire to make a profit;
- they believe that entrepreneurs should have qualities such as leaning on the strengths of their character.

H.R.Hamroev in the educational manual "Fundamentals of Entrepreneurship" (2010) singles out the following. For example, "entrepreneurship, as some people think, is not a passing thing characteristic of the transition period to a market economy, but has a fundamental character. Because it is a phenomenon characteristic not only of the market economy system, but also of all socio-economic systems. Moreover, it is not only an integral part of the economy, but also its driving force. There are those who understand entrepreneurship as business and say that both can be called with one business term. However, the essence of the concept of entrepreneurship is wider and deeper than that of the concept of business. Only business based on entrepreneurship can be called entrepreneurship. But not all businesses are like that. In addition, entrepreneurship exists outside of business."

According to F.Bozorova (2012) and others, a person is a stable system of socially important features characterizing an individual as a member of society. At the same time, he also puts forward the idea that along with the individual, there is a separate representative of the human race - the individual, and the set of characteristics that distinguish this individual from others - the concepts of individuality. Also, the concept of motivation has several meanings in science, and from a psychological point of view, motivation is understood as the process of the employee's subjective activity.

In R.Kh.Ayupov's book "Fundamentals of Entrepreneurial Culture" (2020), "When any entrepreneur starts his business, he uses all his knowledge, skills, experience and money to successfully run his business. In this, he often follows his life experience, the knowledge he received at the educational institution he studied, the set of knowledge he learned from his parents or close people, and some ethical rules. But often this alone is not enough for an entrepreneur's work to be more successful than it is now and to develop further," he says, expressing his attitude to the issues related to the organization of business activities.

In our opinion, improving not only social but also cognitive skills is one of the important factors in improving economic competencies. From a psychological perspective, social skills, such as teamwork and communication, help educators solve economic problems and collaborate with other professionals. Cognitive skills, such as problem analysis and economic decision-making, play an important role in the practical application of economic knowledge. Such skills make it easier for future teachers to acquire economic literacy and increase their professional skills.

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